

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF PERSONNEL SUPPORT FOR INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: This article is devoted to a scientific and theoretical analysis of the activities of staffing internal affairs bodies. The article examines the theoretical foundations of the processes of personnel selection, training, and advanced training. Practical mechanisms aimed at forming personnel policy in internal affairs bodies, developing the professional competencies of employees, and increasing the effectiveness of their activities are analyzed. Proposals will also be developed based on existing problems in personnel provision, modern requirements, and foreign experience. The article is aimed at revealing scientific approaches that serve to improve the staffing of the activities of internal affairs bodies.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, personnel support, professional competence, advanced training, personnel policy, scientific and theoretical analysis, security, foreign experience.

Today, the reforms being carried out in the system of internal affairs bodies, especially the training, retraining, and advanced training of personnel, ensuring the legal and social protection of employees, all the conditions created for the effective fulfillment of assigned tasks, undoubtedly serve to transform internal affairs bodies into a socially oriented professional structure that provides timely and high-quality assistance to the population, where every employee considers it their duty to serve the interests of the people.

Research conducted in this area also shows that the successful fulfillment of the tasks assigned to the internal affairs bodies depends, first of all, on the knowledge, professional training, practical and life experience of employees serving in the system, executive discipline and responsibility for the performance of tasks, as well as other factors related to improving the personnel training system.

For this reason, a high level of professional training, moral and ethical education of employees, increasing their responsibility in ensuring the effective fight against crime; the development of the personnel selection and placement system can be considered as the main direction for improving the activities of internal affairs bodies. Because no matter what task we set for ourselves, no matter what problem we need to solve, the matter ultimately comes down to personnel and personnel again.

The measures taken made it possible to increase the effectiveness of the activities of internal affairs bodies, ensure a peaceful and tranquil life for citizens, and prevent the growth of crime in the country.

It is known that today the maintenance of public order and ensuring security, increasing the effectiveness of the fight against crime are ensured by staffing the system of internal affairs bodies with comprehensively trained personnel, their regular physical, spiritual and moral education, retraining and advanced training. Because the level of professional skills and experience of employees makes it possible to make the right decisions in pressing situations.

The implementation of measures aimed at strengthening law and order and legality in the country, the effective organization of the activities of the services and subdivisions of internal affairs bodies entrusted with the implementation of state decisions, and the professional level of personnel involved in the protection of public order and the fight against crime are directly related. Therefore, to achieve the effectiveness of the activities of internal affairs bodies, the issue of providing them with qualified personnel is one of the urgent tasks facing the Ministry today. Therefore, it is advisable to pay special attention to the selection of candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In the internal affairs bodies, measures are constantly being taken to work with personnel, strengthen service discipline and legality among employees, educate them in the spirit of devotion to the Motherland and their profession, train them, improve their qualifications, and enhance their professional and combat training.

Establishing stability, peace and tranquility in society, ensuring unconditional observance of human rights and freedoms is an important condition for achieving the goals of the large-scale reforms being carried out for the further socio-economic development of the country, improving the well-being of the population, and building a legal democratic state.

An integrated legal system has been created in the republic to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, maintain public order, ensure the security of the individual, society, and the state, and prevent and suppress offenses, in which internal affairs bodies play an important role.

Internal affairs bodies are state law enforcement agencies that protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, as well as the interests of society and the state, from various unlawful pressures. Internal affairs bodies perform the functions of strengthening legality and law and order, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, and combating crime. The importance of the law enforcement function of internal affairs bodies increases even more in the context of the formation of a legal state and the building of civil society.

The adoption of important decisions on the organization of service in the internal affairs bodies, the introduction of an effective system of management, control, and work with personnel contributes to a reduction in violations of official discipline and offenses by employees of the system.

Sharply increasing the effectiveness and efficiency of spiritual-educational, educational-preventive, and ideological work carried out with personnel, **The conceptual idea of "Serving the interests of the people"** is being raised to a completely new level.

A program of targeted measures has been developed to further enhance the effectiveness of work on strengthening service discipline and legality in internal affairs bodies, targeted training and continuous professional development of employees, and their upbringing in the spirit of devotion to the Motherland and their profession.

In our country, the processes of protecting the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the property of individuals and legal entities, the constitutional order, ensuring the security of the individual, society, and the state, as well as ensuring the prevention and prophylaxis of offenses, are becoming increasingly complex and pressing. The processes of effective implementation of these tasks are directly related to the activities of internal affairs bodies in working with personnel.

The functions of internal affairs bodies in organizing personnel work are assigned to the

personnel service and its structural subdivisions on the basis of current legislation. Personnel units of internal affairs bodies are one of the independent structural subdivisions of internal affairs bodies, the main activity of which is related to the admission of citizens to the service of internal affairs bodies, appointment to positions, promotion and transfer to other positions, as well as ensuring professional training, providing legal and social assistance to employees and their families, compliance with official discipline and legislation, and the implementation of state policy in the field of organizational and staffing work.

Based on these reforms, a Program of Comprehensive Measures for the Fundamental Reform of the Internal Affairs Bodies System was approved. Clause 3 of the Program provides for issues of strengthening personnel potential through the introduction of advanced mechanisms for training, selection, and placement of personnel, improving their qualifications and spiritual and moral qualities.

The reforms being carried out in the system *firstly*, can ensure the effective fulfillment of the main tasks assigned to the internal affairs bodies and the new tasks imposed on them based on modern requirements, *secondly*, by the norms of international law, officials of law enforcement agencies, as well as on the basis of the requirements of national legislation, require civil servants, in particular, employees of internal affairs bodies, to be professional specialists with high moral, ethical, and professional qualities.

Personnel work in the system of internal affairs bodies is a complex and multifaceted process, and **the main tasks of** its organization are:

- 1) organization of the selection, study and placement of employees of internal affairs bodies, formation of a reserve of managerial personnel and work with them;
- 2) analysis and assessment of the state of personnel work, determination of priority areas for its further improvement and strengthening of the personnel potential of internal affairs bodies;
- 3) timely detection, suppression, and prevention of instances of abuse of office, corruption, and other unlawful acts by employees;
- 4) organization of professional, physical, and combat training of personnel;
- 5) organization of the process of training, retraining and advanced training of employees;
- 6) ensuring the training of scientific and scientific-pedagogical personnel in educational institutions of the internal affairs bodies;
- 7) organization of moral and educational work with employees, encouragement and disciplinary action;
- 8) taking measures to suppress instances of interference in the lawful activities of employees;
- 9) organization of healthcare for employees, payment of wages, provision of housing, compensation for damage caused to the property of internal affairs officers or their close relatives in connection with the performance of official duties, state pension provision, state insurance, as well as social assistance to employees and their families in accordance with the law;
- 10) ensuring the combat and mobilization training of personnel.

As is known, the selection of candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies consists of a set of interconnected actions that form the content of the following stages and have a defined sequence:

- 1) determination of requirements for the professional and personal qualities of candidates;
- 2) study and assessment of the abilities and personal qualities of specific candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies;
- 3) comparison of the abilities and personal qualities of specific candidates for service in the internal affairs bodies with the requirements for the professional and personal qualities of candidates;
- 4) comparison of candidates based on their abilities and personal qualities;
- 5) selection of the most suitable candidates for internal affairs bodies in terms of requirements for the professional and personal qualities of candidates.
- 6) Over the past period, large-scale work has been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. Significant work has been done, in particular, on the development and strengthening of the lower level of internal affairs bodies, organized to maintain public order in mahallas, ensure the safety of citizens, prevent offenses, and combat crime.
- 7) In Uzbekistan, civil society institutions play an invaluable role in further strengthening the guarantees of the human being, their life, freedom, honor, dignity, and other inalienable rights, recognized as the highest value, and in realizing their aspirations.
- 8) The inextricable link between the concepts of independence, the Constitution, civil society, and democracy is of great importance. Indeed, it is impossible to imagine an independent country without a democratic state governed by the rule of law and strong civil society institutions. Therefore, from the very first days of independence, the path of democratic renewal and the building of a free civil society was chosen in our country. Consequently, everyone traverses this path in their own unique way. Uzbekistan, based on the fundamental principles of democracy and strictly adhering to them, is currently conducting its actions in accordance with the thinking and millennia-old way of life of our people.
- 9) Legality and legal order in society are established by the lawful actions of citizens, the observance of laws by all state bodies and public associations, and their proper use. Establishing stability, peace, and tranquility in society, ensuring unconditional observance of human rights and freedoms, is an important condition for achieving the goals of the large-scale reforms being carried out for the further socio-economic development of the country, improving the well-being of the population, and building a legal democratic state.
- 10) An integrated legal system has been created in the republic for the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the protection of public order, ensuring the security of the individual, society, and the state, and the prevention and prophylaxis of offenses, in which internal affairs bodies play an important role.
- 11) As mentioned above, internal affairs bodies fulfill the tasks of strengthening legality and law and order, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens, and combating crime. Carry out inquiries and preliminary investigations in cases within their competence, ensure peace and the security of humanity. The importance of the implementation of the tasks of internal affairs bodies increases even more in the context of the formation of a legal state and the building of civil society.

In his festive congratulations to the employees and veterans of the sphere on the occasion of the 30th anniversary of the formation of the internal affairs bodies and the celebration of October 25 - the Day of Internal Affairs Workers, the President of our country

also touched upon the direction of personnel training in the internal affairs bodies. In particular, "a completely new system of training specialists has been established, and systemic measures are being taken to ensure professional growth of employees depending on their qualifications, as well as to increase the professional potential of managers. A modern two-level higher education system, including bachelor's and master's degrees, has been introduced at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and new educational mechanisms have been introduced to ensure the integration of theory and practice into the educational process.

Also, in order to increase the personnel potential in the system of internal affairs bodies, and to train personnel who strive for innovation and think modernly, "Temurbeklar Maktabi" and a specialized boarding school, as well as academic lyceums in all regions, have begun operating. Based on modern requirements, new departments specializing in ensuring safe tourism, probation, and combating cybercrime have been established, and training qualified personnel in these areas is one of the main tasks today.

For the high-quality implementation by internal affairs bodies of tasks to protect the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens, the property of individuals and legal entities, the constitutional order, ensure the rule of law, the security of the individual, society, and the state, as well as the prevention and prophylaxis of offenses, the processes of training, retraining, and continuous professional development of personnel in internal affairs bodies are of great importance.

One of the urgent tasks in the field of management of the internal affairs bodies of Uzbekistan is the effective organization of professional and combat training of internal affairs officers.

It is established that citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan capable of fulfilling the official duties of an employee due to their health condition and physical fitness are accepted for service in the internal affairs bodies on a competitive basis. Also, before entering service in the internal affairs bodies, men must undergo compulsory military service in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan or military service in the mobilization call-up reserve, or undergo military training in higher educational institutions.

Internal affairs bodies are one of the most effective structures included in the system of state law enforcement agencies. They perform various, complex, and extremely important functions for maintaining public order, combating crime, ensuring the peaceful life of society and the state, and carrying out other law enforcement activities related to the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of man and citizen.

At the same time, the fulfillment of the tasks facing the internal affairs bodies largely determines the relevance of the issues of personnel composition, their professional skills, moral-psychological and spiritual-educational training, as well as the effective protection of the legitimate rights and interests of citizens, ensuring the security of the state and society, primarily the training of personnel of the internal affairs bodies and improving their professional and combat training.

Issues related to improving the professional and combat training of internal affairs officers are of particular importance in the effective implementation of personnel policy. Today, employees of internal affairs bodies face many non-standard situations, the resolution of which sometimes largely depends on their patriotism and professional skills, the ability to act in strict accordance with the law. The formation of these and other necessary qualities of

employees of internal affairs bodies should be ensured by an effective system of professional and combat training in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized, "We are seriously working on creating an effective system for training personnel who think in new ways and independently, are responsible, proactive, have mastered advanced management methods, are honest, devoted to their Homeland and people....The people themselves will evaluate the activities of leaders based on the level of trust in them and the level of effective solution of problems that concern the population"[1].

To implement the words of the Head of State, every head of the internal affairs bodies must critically review and analyze their activities, not only reprimand subordinates who have made mistakes and shortcomings in their work, but also carry out targeted work to improve their knowledge and professional skills. In this case, it is advisable to organize classes with the involvement of employees.

For example, it would be beneficial to establish two days a week and, based on workload, organize additional training sessions for 30-40 minutes during the month to convey the main content of current or newly adopted regulatory legal documents, internal affairs bodies in other regions, or foreign experience to personnel. Subsequently, depending on their abilities, it is also necessary to involve employees as keynote speakers in the sessions. This not only increases the legal knowledge of employees, but also serves to encourage employees to strive for innovation, analyze information, and develop pedagogical skills.

Every leader should be not only a manager, but also a modern manager and a skilled teacher who acts as a mentor to his subordinates. To achieve the goals we have set for ourselves today, every leader must be a leader who knows, analyzes, and finds solutions to problems in the field, capable of leading his subordinates. For this, managers must first of all constantly improve their knowledge and implement targeted measures to improve the knowledge of their employees. A leader who avoids this, citing excuses like "I don't know this field, I'm not a specialist," always pulls the field backward. Similarly, a manager who sees his subordinates as competitors also disrupts the system, otherwise the industry will flourish, in a word, there will be upward-moving progress.

Information provided by the responsible body or official, defined by the current regulatory legal acts on the activities of all sectoral services of internal affairs bodies and their structural subdivisions, is accessible to everyone, that is, any restrictions are not allowed, taking into account the social status of the user or other circumstances. In addition, information on the activities of internal affairs bodies must be provided in a timely manner, at the time established by current legislation. In any case, the information provided regarding the activities of internal affairs bodies must be reliable, that is, based on accurate facts and information, and verified in advance.

Openness and transparency of the activities of internal affairs bodies, that is, the sectoral service and its structural subdivisions must carry out their activities openly, in the presence of others and without concealment from them. For example, a prevention inspector or a responsible employee of the road safety service is required to draw up a report and other documents on an identified administrative offense in the presence of the person who committed the offense, witnesses, with an open explanation of their rights. However, when carrying out operational-search activities of internal affairs bodies, in particular, certain investigative actions, restrictions are allowed based on the requirements of current

legislation, namely the norms of the Criminal Procedure Code, the Law on Operational-Search Activities, as well as departmental regulatory legal acts[2].

In conclusion, it can be said that the work on implementing a system based on the principle of "Prosperous and Safe Mahalla" to ensure public order and early prevention of offenses in mahallas has been accelerated. Today, completely new mechanisms for organizing the activities of internal affairs bodies are being introduced. In particular, problems related to crime prevention and combating crime are being solved directly on the ground by identifying and eliminating the causes of crime at the level of each mahalla, family, and individual.

Literature:

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